

LEWIS CARROLL'S *ALICE'S ADVENTURES IN WONDERLAND* – AN INEXHAUSTIBLE SOURCE OF EMOTIONAL EXPRESSION AND EMOTIONALLY (IL)LITERATE PATTERNS OF MANIFESTATION

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Literature is approached because of the richness of thoughts and feelings to which readers gain access. Lewis Carroll's Alice's Adventures in Wonderland provokes the readership to a vigorous exercise in perceiving emotional subtleties beyond words and in discovering a profound meaning in the emotional manifestations of characters. The illocutionary and the perlocutionary speech acts (Austin J. L., 1962) exert here a stronger force when analysed from the perspective of emotional intelligence. The present paper focuses on the way the book may be approached from the perspective of The Four-Branch Model of Emotional Intelligence designed by John D. Mayer and Peter Salovey in order to raise the awareness regarding the force of emotions, what triggers them and what makes someone an emotionally literate person.

Keywords: feelings, speech acts, emotional intelligence, emotional literacy skills.

Lewis Carroll's *Alice's Adventures in Wonderland* has constantly been a source of inspiration and puzzlement due to its abounding richness in word patterns and behavioural surprises, in changes that affect not only the characters in the book but also the readers involved in a vivid transaction with the text. In William Empson's words, the book – together with *Through the Looking Glass* – is “so frankly about growing up” (Empson, 2006, p. 39) and has at its core “a shift onto the child” (Empson, 2006, p. 40) that it freshly appeals to adults as well, especially to those who are ready to face the world of children and make sense of all the inner struggles involved in the constant physical growing and psychological development.

Research in the field of psychology at the end of the 20th century and the beginning of the 21st laid special emphasis on integrating emotion into cognitive science, since “far from being the opposite of thought, emotion is now viewed as intimately bound up with thought, to such an extent that one cannot fully understand cognition without understanding emotion, and one cannot fully understand emotion without fully understanding cognition.” (Hogan, 2003, p. 140) Therefore, a closer look at the knowledge delivered by the book – even if at a first glance it may seem nonsensical – and the emotions accompanying its delivery, will offer insights into the way the words used may trigger expected or unexpected reactions.

The *Four-Branch Ability Model of Emotional Intelligence* proposed by the psychologists John D. Mayer and Peter Salovey (Mayer and Salovey, 1997, p. 11) offers a ranking of abilities from those perceived by the authors as “simple” (p. 10) to those that involve higher mental processes. Each branch presents a gradual consideration of aspects involved in mental and emotional processing and use of information. Moreover, each level relies on competences from the areas of intrapersonal, interpersonal and linguistic intelligences as they are all involved in the encounter with literary texts and in the making of each human being.

The first branch – *Perception, Appraisal, and Expression of Emotion* – includes the basic abilities of identifying emotions in one’s own physical states, feelings and thoughts, the ability to identify emotions in other people through language, appearance and behaviour, the ability to express emotions accurately and to express needs related to them, as well as the ability to discriminate between honest and dishonest expressions of feelings, this last one being probably the subtler of all and mainly the privilege of adults. From this perspective, what Lewis Carroll does is to make readers aware of all the inner workings of Alice’s mind and of the instances when she is aware of the way the encounters with the characters from wonderland affect her and the others emotionally. Alice is a proficient decoder of emotions in herself and others and fully engaged in becoming competent in understanding the adults’ juggling with the words and the meanings that accompany or convey emotions.

The epitome of Alice’s struggle to make sense of herself in this ‘mad’ and ‘maddening’ world resonates in her question “Who in the world am I?” (Carroll, 1994, p. 24) and then ““Who am I then? [...] if I like, being that person, I’ll come up: if not, I’ll stay down here till I’m somebody else”” (Carroll, 1994, p. 25) as if she had a choice about her own identity and the person she would like to be when coming into the world. The constant directing of thoughts towards her own person and identity culminates in very mature ponderings: ““But it’s no use now,’ thought poor Alice, ‘to pretend to be two people! Why, there’s hardly enough for me left to make one respectable person!’” (Carroll, 1994, p. 19) Nevertheless, she finely disposes of emotional literacy skills everyone should master: she advises or scolds herself (p. 19), activities that point to a keen observance of the self with its own emotional needs. All these ponderings on her emotional states coupled with those triggered by the bodily transformations that either make her fit or unfit for the changing circumstances indicate the constant mental activity of a growing person that needs and wants to make sense of oneself for one’s own sake and the sake of others. The fact that she is monitoring her words and feelings so as not to hurt others is clearly supported by her earnest attempts to stifle her natural reactions and assertions before it is too late – instances that sometimes lead to funny occurrences:

“Thank you, it’s a very interesting dance to watch,’ said Alice, feeling very glad that it was over at last: ‘and I do so like that curious song about the whiting!’

‘Oh, as to the whiting,’ said the Mock Turtle, ‘they—you’ve seen them, of course?’

‘Yes,’ said Alice, ‘I’ve often seen them at dinn—’ she checked herself hastily.

‘I don’t know where Dinn may be,’ said the Mock Turtle, ‘but if you’ve seen them so often, of course you know what they’re like.’” (Carroll, 1994, pp. 120-121)

The second branch is the *Emotional Facilitation of Thinking* and focuses on the role of emotions in prioritizing thinking. The force of emotions can be noted in the degree of attention they raise towards the contextual input so that they may aid towards a fair judgment of the situation and the appropriate response demanded by the situation. This branch also incorporates the ‘emotional mood swings’ that steer an individual’s perspective and allows for multiple points of view and encourages ‘specific problem approaches’ (Mayer and Salovey, 1997, p. 11). The mood in wonderland seems to gravitate around a certain *anxiety, sadness, and moodiness*, frequently sprinkled with moments of wonder at the queerness of things. On the other hand, the adjective ‘curious’ for example, suggestive of children’s way of thinking and perceiving and of Alice’s reactions to the happenings and characters in wonderland, occurs with such frequency that one has to wonder about all the shades of meaning it carries depending on the instances or utterances that demand such labelling. Almost everything in this wonder world makes Alice exclaim – even when the form is not the grammatically correct one – ‘Curiouser and curiouser!’ (Carroll, 1994, p. 21)

The third branch raises the level of competence to the finer intellectual abilities revolving around *Understanding and Analysing Emotions and Employing Emotional Knowledge*. The core competence here is the ability to label emotions, to see the relation between emotions and words and to assign the appropriate meaning to the emotions. Moreover, as the feelings become more complex – given the situations that trigger surprising combinations thereof and the unexpected transitions from

one to another – so should the ability to recognize the various effects and to respond accordingly. The verbal exchanges seem to challenge Alice to an active exercise of being aware of the effect of her words on others together with a heartfelt attempt to make up for the hurt feelings:

“Not like cats!” cried the Mouse, in a shrill, passionate voice. ‘Would you like cats if you were me?’

‘Well, perhaps not,’ said Alice in a soothing tone: ‘don’t be angry about it. And yet I wish I could show you our cat Dinah: I think you’d take a fancy to cats if you could only see her. She is such a dear quiet thing,’ [...] I beg your pardon!’ cried Alice again, for this time the Mouse was bristling all over, and she felt certain it must be really offended.” (Carroll, 1994, pp. 28-29)

The characters in wonderland seem to be closely attached to certain moods so that even the swings are predictable. The authorial mastery resides in the verbal twists and turns that do cause strong emotions. It is through his choice of words that the readers gain direct access to the emotions of characters and to some less subtle lessons in manners:

“‘Have some wine,’ the March Hare said in an encouraging tone.

Alice looked all round the table, but there was nothing on it but tea. ‘I don’t see any wine,’ she remarked.

‘There isn’t any,’ said the March Hare.

‘Then it wasn’t very civil of you to offer it,’ said Alice angrily.

‘It wasn’t very civil of you to sit down without being invited,’ said the March Hare.” (Carroll, 1994, p. 80)

The fourth branch – *Reflective Regulation of Emotions to Promote Emotional and Intellectual Growth* – is focused on people’s ability to reflect on and manage emotions based on the knowledge one gains on the force of emotions and on the need to face them with an equally matching stamina. Staying open to feelings, a key skill in this final chain of abilities, together with actively and reflectively engaging or detaching from an emotion as well as monitoring the emotions in self and others culminate in a wise management of emotions which is expected from and desirable for all of us. The author gives enough hints regarding Alice’s openness to feelings and the manner in which she engages or discreetly detaches from unpleasant ones. The readers discover that she handles situations and manages her own emotions with a poise fit for a balanced, emotionally and behaviourally insightful adult: Alice “replied very politely”, “felt a little irritated [...] and said, very gravely” or swallowed “down her anger as well as she could” (Carroll, 1994, pp. 54-55).

Alice’s Adventures in Wonderland is a tale heavily relying on dialogue – be it inner or outer. Therefore, Austin’s theory of speech acts complements *The Four-Branch Model of Emotional Intelligence* and gains further depth due to the character’s habit of using words and then pondering on the way they were uttered and the significance they may gain. The *locutionary* speech act, which refers to the production of an utterance and the performance of the act of speaking, assumes a new dimension with the playfulness of the author who applies a kind of mathematical formula that actually cannot lead to the same logical result. The palindromic reversals make the interlocutors think of the sense implications of utterances as: “I mean what I say” is not the same as “I say what I mean” just like “I see what I eat” is not the same thing as “I eat what I see”, “I like what I get” and “I get what I like” or “I breathe when I sleep” and “I sleep when I breathe” (Carroll, 1994, p. 82). Many characters in the book – especially the Hatter, the March Hare and the Mock Turtle – have a special gift of introducing verbal incongruities in their communication and these may stir strong emotions but are satirically hinting at some striking truths. These utterances can be further considered from the perspective of the other two speech acts mentioned by Austin: the *illocutionary* – a speech act that can be classified according to its force (stating, praising, threatening, warning, promising, etc.) and the *perlocutionary* – an act meant to have an effect upon the feelings, thoughts, or actions of the interlocutors (Austin J. L., 1962). The verbal exchanges in the book rely on the frequent use of

imperatives or questions and even if their frankness shocks at times, they are meant to have a strong emotional impact on the interlocutors.

What strikes even more is the perception of the utterances in a world dominated by creatures that seem to be immersed in a rather gloomy mood. The words referring to emotions bear slightly negative connotations: there is a pervasive *anger* that may spark at the merest unaccepted remark – the word appears in various derivatives: *anger* (twice), *angry* (five times) and *angrily* (nine times) being very suggestive of the emotionally laden conversations in the book. Less frequently occurring, but in the same area of strong feelings are: *nervous* (five times), *annoy* (once) – *annoyed* (once). Losing one's temper is another emotion Alice experiences especially since her logic is being challenged all the way through wonderland.

The encounters with the situations and various creatures trigger another extreme emotion – that of *fright*. Therefore, the readers find out that Alice experiences this emotion quite often – the word *frightened* occurs for five times in relation to her, *twice* in relation to other creatures and then the noun *fright* and the verb *frighten* complete the morphological picture with three more occurrences.

Probably the most frequently employed words for feelings are: *glad* and *anxious*, which can be naturally linked to the emotional world of children. *Glad* – a word frequently used to refer to Alice – gives adults a glimpse into the things that make children experience this feeling. The author informs the readers about the instances in which Alice feels *glad*: when no knowledgeable witness is in sight to judge her lack of precise knowledge, when she finds herself still in existence after narrowly escaping the danger of shrinking completely, when ready to show off her knowledge, when promised a game of riddles, when she has someone listen to her, when she finds her interlocutor (the Duchess) in a pleasant temper, when she realizes that there are better gifts offered at birthdays in the real world than the mere offering of someone's words, when an unpleasant activity is over and she does not have the courage to openly express her opinion about it (due to her good manners), when asked to stop reciting verses she could not remember exactly, and when seeing how things are being done at trials (although the nonsense of the act itself in this upside town world is obvious). All these may prove useful for adults who really intend to understand the emotional world of children and build strong emotional bonds with them.

Anxiety is also a pervasive feeling in wonderland, probably because – just like its dictionary definition suggests [1] – it is “an uncomfortable feeling of nervousness or worry about something that is happening or might happen in the future; something that causes a feeling of fear and worry; eagerness to do something”, a feeling so commonly experienced by children in their growing stages. The adverb *anxiously* is related to Alice's wonderings regarding the path to take, her fear of catching a cold, her trying to help as she was “always ready to make herself useful” (Carroll, 1994, p. 38), when she finds herself in unknown places and does not know what to do, when expecting the reactions of others, and when trying to make sense of the condition of others. The Rabbit's activities in the book are also performed quite *anxiously* – when afraid of what others may do to him, when looking at Alice or looking around. The Mock Turtle, the Hatter, the King also act *anxiously* depending on the circumstances. The cards are behaving *anxiously*, especially when the irritable Queen is approaching. The servants of the Queen are *anxious* at the threat of being executed if something is not done quickly.

The utterances that seemingly bind all the speech acts into a meaningful whole are the moral teachings readers may infer or the ones the Duchess directly draws from all verbal instances:

“’Tis so,’ said the Duchess: ‘and the moral of that is—“Oh, ‘tis love, ‘tis love, that makes the world go round!” ’

‘Somebody said,’ Alice whispered, ‘that it’s done by everybody minding their own business!’

‘Ah, well! It means much the same thing,’ said the Duchess, digging her sharp little chin into Alice’s shoulder as she added, ‘and the moral of that is—“Take care of the sense, and the sounds will take care of themselves.” ’ (Carroll, 1994, p. 107)

With this last moral the readers should gain the subtlest understanding of the force of utterances – if one knows what the sense or the meaning of an utterance is, then the choice of words and the way they should sound to accomplish the expected effect should certainly not pose any problem. The focus here is on meaning and sense making as the root of all communication.

The frequency of *perlocutionary* speech acts can be traced throughout the book not only in the encounters between various characters, but also in the solitude of Alice facing the novelty of this strange new world, the surprising inner struggles she has to face and the inner dialogue she has. Trapped in a world in which she undergoes lots of physical transformations and being confronted with a reversing logic of words and a bizarre distortion of sentence order and word order, Alice is on the verge of *hopelessness* and bursts into tears, meaning that she has reached the extreme level of *despair*: “‘I’m sure those are not the right words,’ said poor Alice, and her eyes filled with tears” (Carroll, 1994, p. 25) However, even in this desperate state she is fully aware of the cause and the effects of her own emotions and scolds herself just like adults might do to children: “‘You ought to be ashamed of yourself,’ said Alice, ‘a great girl like you,’ (she might well say this), ‘to go on crying in this way! Stop this moment, I tell you!’ But she went on all the same, shedding gallons of tears, until there was a large pool all round her, about four inches deep and reaching half down the hall.” (Carroll, 1994, p. 22) and then she deems the consequences of so much crying in the real world, although she is surprised by the nonsense of it as well: “‘I wish I hadn’t cried so much!’ said Alice, as she swam about, trying to find her way out. ‘I shall be punished for it now, I suppose, by being drowned in my own tears! That will be a queer thing, to be sure! However, everything is queer to-day.’” (Carroll, 1994, p. 27)

The fact that the story revolves around her growing is rendered in the weird physical changes she experiences while trapped in the apparently confining spaces and by the echoes of adults’ verbal patterns that pierce the text and make her ponder more on her own actions and words. Carroll’s surreal intervention in the text is once more obvious in Alice’s awareness of her positioning in the plot:

“‘I do wonder what can have happened to me! When I used to read fairy-tales, I fancied that kind of thing never happened, and now here I am in the middle of one! There ought to be a book written about me, that there ought! And when I grow up, I’ll write one— but I’m grown up now,’ she added in a sorrowful tone; ‘at least there’s no room to grow up any more here.’ ‘But then,’ thought Alice, ‘shall I never get any older than I am now? That’ll be a comfort, one way—never to be an old woman— but then—always to have lessons to learn! Oh, I shouldn’t like that!’” (Carroll, 1994, p. 43)

The playful self-awareness is even more vivid in the way Alice perceives her bodily transformations and talks about her own feet: “‘I must be kind to them,’ thought Alice, ‘or perhaps they won’t walk the way I want to go!’” (Carroll, 1994, p. 22)

The unexpected changes in the logic and order of things and the chosen channels of mediating ideas through diverse creatures are meant to keep the readers wondering and pondering in order to make sense and decode meaning. This is probably the book for children that should be read by adults to get a glimpse of these ones’ perspective on the world. It is a vivid lesson in rightfully manipulating words to deliver meaningful messages and in making sense of circumstances in order to come out victoriously. Alice has descended into a mad world, but she is capable – despite her moments of despair and hopelessness – to be anchored in a logical reality by means of her awareness of herself and the truth culminating in her last remark: “‘Who cares for you?’ said Alice, (she had grown to her full size by this time.) ‘You’re nothing but a pack of cards!’” (Carroll, 1994, p. 145) Her inner dialogue reveals her struggles and the wish to interact with the others so that there will be no ill feelings ensuing. She emerges as the most emotionally literate being in a world of so diverse and mainly emotionally illiterate characters that seem on the verge of bursting into fits of anger at the slightest hint or mistake.

Since emotions can obviously be read on people’s faces, Carroll’s opting for illustrations may have added to the artfulness of offering readers a glimpse into the way the characters feel. John

Tenniel's illustrations of the book capture the emotions of the characters with the mastery of the discreet but accurate observer – the worry on the rabbit's face, the surprise on Alice's face when she feels growing and “opening like a large microscope” (Carroll, 1994, p. 21), the fright when she floats in the pool of her own tears, the sorrow and unhappiness when trapped in the house in which she grew to the point of feeling really uncomfortable due to the lack of space.

The book's openness to various interpretations has inspired various artists who have rendered the illustrations of the book in different manners and styles [2] – ranging from joyfully childlike to conspicuously gothic, most of them choosing to render the facial expressions in a way that is suggestive of the feelings of characters. However, maybe the best artist who managed to transpose the dreamlike atmosphere and the emotional and interactional subtleties of the text and the hints to the distressing process of growing into adulthood is Salvador Dali [3], a master of surrealism, who opts for only hinting at the way the characters look and delivering a message about their feelings and interactions through the colours and the symbols he used. He even inserted many of his symbols into the illustrations of *Alice's Adventures in Wonderland*: the melting clock – a symbol of fluidity, of time bending in the ‘heat’ of the events and according to the perception and the experience of each character (the Rabbit being out of time; the time being perceived differently or being chronologically distorted through the reversed order of things done or said); a projection of the crutch in the silhouette of Alice to indicate her stability in spite of the madness of the others and the maddening circumstances and utterances; the butterflies, carrying with them the idea of metamorphosis, the emergence of the adult creature from the ‘caterpillar’. The shadows that the creatures and objects cast reflect the mirror-like picture that is at the heart of the verbal and interactional matter of the text. It is an upside down projection of reality, one that compels all the thinking and feeling abilities in order to make sense and bring sense to the narrative. The artist – through the choice of colours – manages to create a sort of mood pervading the narrative. If we were to judge the choice of colours to render the intensity of emotions according to the Mood Meter devised by psychologist Marc Brackett [4], when there is tension in the narrative – like the Caucus Race and a Long Tale, the Mad Tea Party, and Who Stole the Tarts?, Dali opted for hues of red indicative of irritation, uneasiness, even fury. When there's a hint to Alice's feeling rather low on energy – down the Rabbit Hole – Dali used blue together with other shades of red, green and yellow to highlight the complex mix of feelings Alice is experiencing in this falling into wonderland: uneasiness, surprise, serenity, and a little bit of fatigue. Dali anticipates thus an age when recipients of works of art and people in general have to be better emotionally literate to identify emotions and hints on emotional states in order to be able to cope verbally and behaviourally.

Reading *Alice's Adventures in Wonderland* from the perspective of emotional intelligence and the theory of speech acts makes one think of the importance of having a keen awareness of emotions and the way they are expressed – subtly or bluntly, of the necessity to adopt a multilateral perspective on things, people and circumstances, of the need to be able to master one's feelings and verbal output when situations are challenging and above all of the necessity to be aware of the reality and its changing nature. Alice proves that being emotionally literate means having the ability to see oneself acting and speaking, to analyse triggers and responses, to artfully manage the impact of people and circumstances on oneself and to know when to put an end to what is deemed unpleasant and not edifying.

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